

OLLSCOIL NA GAILLIMHE
UNIVERSITY OF GALWAY

High Performance Thermoplastic Composite Pipeline Development with Automated Tape Placement (ATP) Technology

for Energy Industry Applications

“ATP Pipeline” Project

Mr Carlos Bachour Sirerol

Academic Mentors: Dr Noel Harrison (University of Galway)

Industrial Mentor: Dr Tomás Flanagan (ÉireComposites)

ICCM23 Conference

31st July 2023

Offshore

Thermoplastic Composite Pipeline (TCP)

Application

What is a TCP Riser?

Jumpers

Risings

Flowlines

- Mix flow:
- Oil
 - Gas
 - Water
 - Sand

*1 → TLP stands for Tension Leg Platform.

*2 → FPSO stands for Floating Production Storage and Offloading.

Offshore TCPs Materials Selection

Each layer fulfils a different mission → **One Materials Selection / layer**

Ranking using objective: Find the screened materials that do the job best.
Cost-effective mechanical performance. Most representative plot of out of 20.

Liner → HDPE

Intermediate Laminate → CF/PP

Cover → PE-100

Automated Tape Placement ATP Manufacturing

ATP – Pipeline Project

Manufacturing technique selected

Project ID: MF-2018-0036

OLLSCOIL NA
GAILLIMHE
UNIVERSITY
OF GALWAY

Fail it until make it!

A cost – competitive TCP proof-of-concept was developed compatible with Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage (CCUS) applications.

Testing was conducted at laminate and pipe levels to benchmark the chosen material combination.

Research

Further research is needed to enhance liner-to-intermediate layer compatibility and avoid the employment of adhesives.

INNER LINER LAYER

TCP valid for CCUS Applications

Permeability levels of ScCO₂ HCs & Water comparable to Oil & Gas benchmark (PAs)

COVER & INTERMEDIATE REINFORCED LAYERS

Layers are able to supply structural integrity & abrasion resistance

OLLSCOIL NA GAILLIMHE
UNIVERSITY OF GALWAY

THANK YOU

Acknowledgments

Career-FIT has received funding from the European Union's Horizon2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 713654

Supporting Information Project Framework

ATP – Pipeline Project
CO₂ valorisation scheme

Carbon Capture Utilization & Storage (CCUS) Application

... will struggle to sell

... will incur in fines

Organizations without low-C products...

CO₂ Transportation

Government Policies: US "45Q Tax credit"

\$287 million saved in taxes for disposing 500,000 ton CO₂/year in a secure geologic storage over 12 years.

Strategy to get **compatibility** between liner and intermediate laminate

To enhance
compatibility

Match matrix
material with
Liner material

PP liner & CF/PP tape

PE liner & CF/PE tape

